

New Serotonergics with High Intracellular Bioavailability as Potentially Neuroplastic and Geroprotective Agents

Yaroslav G. Zaitsev ORCID: 0000-0002-0069-2997 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18216431>

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Data Availability & Methodology: Targets: 5-HT_{1A}, 2A/B; MAPK/NF-κB; Neurogenics. In Silico: SAR Library (80+ scaffolds); pKi; ADME/Tox. Status: Preprint (2026). License: CC BY 4.0. Contact: nabrosov nabrosov@gmail.com. Author: Ya. G. Zaitsev.

Abstract

Erinacine A (*Hericium erinaceus*) and psilocybin exhibit partially overlapping pharmacological profiles (pKi 5-HT ≈ 6.3 and 7.2 in silico respectively), but differ significantly in lipophilicity and the type of neuroplasticity induced. Carvacrol ([Sisti et al., 2021](#)), α-bisabolol ([Kim et al., 2025](#)), and β-asarone ([Dong et al., 2014](#)), which share serotonergic properties (Figure), also show potential as neurotrophic agents.

Furthermore, activation of 5-HT receptors leads to the upregulation of CREB and NF-κB/MAPK signaling pathways, thereby inducing neurogenesis, also serotonergic structures are aimed at targeted induction of BDNF in learning and memory areas CA1 and CA3 of the hippocampus ([Jiang et al., 2016](#)). This mechanism has been demonstrated by several lipophilic agents, including antidepressants like captodiamine ([Ring & Regan, 2013](#)) and neuroprotective terpenes such as carvacrol, α-bisabolol ([Arunachalam et al., 2022](#)), and β-asarone. The neurogenic potential of these compounds correlates with their affinity for 5-HT receptors (Figure). Similarly, schisandrins ([Li et al., 2019](#)) (in silico pKi ≈ 6.58) from *Schisandra chinensis* and ginsenosides ([Han et al., 2024](#)) (in silico pKi ≈ 6.4) from *Panax ginseng* have been extensively documented as potent neuroprotective and neurotrophic agents.

Fast neuroplasticity (e.g., psilocybin ([Golden et al., 2022](#)), ketamine ([Kopelman et al., 2023](#))) promotes synaptogenesis but can duplicate pathological connections and increase neural noise. In contrast, slow neuroplasticity—true neurogenesis and myelinogenesis—appears to be more beneficial for organic brain damage, depression, Alzheimer's disease, and related conditions. The lipophilic and amphiphilic synthetic terpenes and tryptophols presented in this study are designed for deep (intracellular) neurotrophic activity, targeting 5-HT_{1A} receptors and potential allosteric sites. This is achieved through both deep regional penetration averaged mimetics and the selectivity of some candidates with high 5-HT_{1A} affinity, as confirmed by in silico analysis (<https://serotoninai.streamlit.app>).

Study structures exhibit varying levels of affinity (from moderate to high- pKi ≈ 7.8), different gradations of selectivity, high lipophilicity, and excellent bioavailability. Their deep penetration hypothetically ensures sustained "slow neuroplasticity" and more comprehensive 5-HT modulation. Furthermore, this study presents potential pharmacological analogs of hericenones: ultra-lipophilic lipophilic serotonin mimetics with potential activity within myelin sheaths and axons. Finally, psilocybin has also been shown to extend replicative lifespan by up to 50% through telomerase modulation and reduction of oxidative stress ([Kato et al., 2025](#)).

Keywords: Erinacine A, hericenones, *Herichium erinaceus*, neurotrophic agents, rational drug design, non-psychedelic neuroplasticity, slow neuroplasticity, lipophilic 5-HT1A mimetics, NGF/BDNF induction, telomerase modulation, geroprotectors, MAPK/NF- κ B signaling, in silico screening, SAR library.

1. Introduction

Figure

Reference compounds: Carvacrol – β -Asarone – α -Bisabolol – Hericenones – Erinacine A – Psilocybin

pKi 5-HT_{1A}: α -Bisabolol – 5.15, Carvacrol – 5.4, β -Asarone – 5.4, Hericenones – 5.753, Erinacine A – 6.052, Psilocin – 7.0

pKi 5-HT_{2A}: β -Asarone – 5.2, Carvacrol – 5.236, Hericenones – 5.889, α -Bisabolol – 6.11, Erinacine A – 6.207, Psilocin – 7.2

pKi 5-HT_{2B}: α -Bisabolol – 5.57, β -Asarone – 5.78, Carvacrol – 5.794, Hericenones – 5.921, Erinacine A – 6.264, Psilocin – 6.34

2. Rationale and Proposed Structures

Natural neurotrophic terpenes and terpenoids often exhibit their activity due to their ultra-high lipophilicity, despite the spatial noise of random radicals and suboptimal pharmacophoric positions. Low receptor affinity, low mimetic capacity, suboptimal bioavailability, limited physicochemical diversity, as well as inherent difficulties in purification and production, are insurmountable obstacles to full-fledged pharmacological practice. In this context, the search for and development of pharmacologically sound, bioavailable, and amphiphilic agents with pronounced neurotrophic activity is a standard solution.

The development of dozens of original core compounds—characterized by specific pharmacokinetic properties, in silico determined activity, strictly graded affinity within a bioavailable amphiphilic profile—represents the path to realizing a full therapeutic spectrum. This spectrum ranges from averaged, pro-native allosteric modulators ([Nguyen et al., 2024](#)), ([Brunetti et al., 2025](#)) based on short pharmacological serotonin analogs to specialized, highly selective, and high-affinity 5-HT1A agents ([Casarotto et al., 2021](#)), ([Jiang et al., 2016](#)), ([Kato et al., 2025](#)).

Table

ID	Chemical Structure	pKi (5-HT _{1A})	pKi (5-HT _{2A})	pKi (5-HT _{2B})	MW(Da)	ClogP	ClogS	ClogD	pKa (basic)	HBA	HBD	TPSA (Å ²)	Lipinski Rule	CNS-MPO	SMILES
E01		6.1	5.5	5.95	203.24	1.92	-2.33	2.12	-2.53	2	2	45.25	Yes (0 violations)	4.5	<chem>COC1=CC=C(C=C1)C=CCO</chem>
E02		6.14	5.21	5.58	220.26	2.78	-3.98	3.05	-4.41	3	0	27.69	Yes (0 violations)	4.9	<chem>COC1=CC=C(C=C1)OCCOCC2=CC=CC=C2OC3CC3</chem>
E03		6.2	5.1	5.7	358.39	2.8	-5.02	3.18	-4.32	6	0	71.06	Yes (0 violations)	5.4	<chem>CCOC1=CC=C(C=C1)OCCOC2=CC=C(C=C2)OC(C)C</chem>
E04		6.2	5.2	5.63	310.39	1.65	-2.77	2.26	-3.62	5	0	46.15	Yes (0 violations)	5.9	<chem>COC1=CC=C(C=C1)OCCOCCOCCOC2=CC=C(C=C2)OC</chem>
E05		6.2	5.7	5.42	302.36	2.88	-4.21	2.89	-3.77	4	0	36.92	Yes (0 violations)	5.4	<chem>C1=CC=C(C=C1)OCCOCCOCC2=CC=CC=C2</chem>
E06		6.2	5.3	6	185.23	2.88	-4.68	2.74	-7.65	1	1	32.86	Yes (0 violations)	5.1	<chem>O=C(C1CC1)C2=CC=C3C=CNC3=C2</chem>

ID	Chemical Structure	pKi (5-HT _{1A})	pKi (5-HT _{2A})	pKi (5-HT _{2B})	MW(Da)	ClogP	ClogS	ClogD	pKa (basic)	HBA	HBD	TPSA (Å ²)	Lipinski Rule	CNS-MPO	SMILES
E07		6.2	5.5	5.6	372.42	3.03	-5.14	3.32	-4.31	6	0	71.06	Yes (0 violations)	5.2	<chem>CCOC1=CC=C(C(=O)C=C1)OCCOC1=CC=C(C(=O)C=C1)OCC</chem>
E08		6.2	6	5.7	238.33	1.57	-2.71	2.67	-3.7	3	0	27.69	Yes (0 violations)	5	<chem>C1CC1OC1CC(OCC2CC2)C(C1)OC1CC1</chem>
E09		6.23	5.5	5.6	232.28	2.29	-3.93	2.68	-4.39	3	0	35.53	Yes (0 violations)	5.4	<chem>COC1=CC(C=C(C(C)=O)C=C1)OC1CC1</chem>
E010		6.23	5.6	5.53	190.24	3.29	-4.34	3.17	-4.57	2	0	18.46	Yes (0 violations)	4.3	<chem>C1CC1OC1=C(C(OC2CC2)=C)C=C1</chem>
E011		6.24	5.42	5.7	294.35	1.68	-3.88	2.09	-3.77	5	0	53.99	Yes (0 violations)	6	<chem>COCCOCCOC1=CC(=CC=C1OC)C(=O)C1CC1</chem>
E012		6.25	5.13	5.7	178.23	2.24	-2.6	2.23	-2.75	2	1	29.46	Yes (0 violations)	5.2	<chem>OCCOC1=CC(=CC=C1)C=C</chem>
E013		6.27	5.4	6.14	187.24	2.3	-2.82	2.39	-3.1	1	2	36.02	Yes (0 violations)	5.1	<chem>OC(C1CC1)C1=CN(C2=C1C=CC=C2)C=C1</chem>

	Chemical Structure	pKi (5-HT _{1A})	pKi (5-HT _{2A})	pKi (5-HT _{2B})	MW(Da)	ClogP	ClogS	ClogD	pKa (basic)	HBA	HBD	TPSA (Å ²)	Lipinski Rule	CNS-MPO	SMILES
E014		6.28	5.6	5.7	190.24	2.65	-2.72	2.69	-3.01	2	1	29.46	Yes (0 violations)	5	<chem>OC1CC1OC1=CC=CC=C1C=C</chem>
E015		6.3	5.8	5.4	254.33	4.41	-5	3.88	-4.56	2	0	18.46	Yes (0 violations)	3.4	<chem>C=CC1=C(C(OCOC2=CC=C(C=C2)C=C1)C=C</chem>
E016		6.3	5.3	5.8	308.42	3.27	-4.21	3.06	-3.64	4	0	36.92	Yes (0 violations)	5.2	<chem>CCC1=C(OCOCOC)C=C(COC2CC2)C=C1</chem>
E017		6.3	5.7	5.5	246.35	4	-5.01	3.67	-4.07	2	0	32.64	Yes (0 violations)	4.3	<chem>C(CC1=CC=C(OC2CCCC2)C=C1)OC1CC1</chem>
E018		6.32	5.7	5.6	246.31	3.89	-5.5	3.57	-4.4	3	0	27.69	Yes (0 violations)	4.2	<chem>C1CC1OC1=C(C(OC2CC2)=C(C(OC2CC2)=C1)OC1CC1</chem>
E019		6.33	5.7	6	173.22	2.97	-3.43	3.12	-4.89	1	1	25.02	Yes (0 violations)	4.5	<chem>C1CC1OC1=C(C=CC2=C1C=C2)N</chem>
E020		6.4	5.3	5.9	296.36	1.59	-2.53	2.44	-3.62	5	0	46.15	Yes (0 violations)	5.8	<chem>COCOCOCOC1=CC(OC)=C(C(OC2CC2)C=C1</chem>
E021		6.4	5.4	6	289.38	3.86	-3.45	3.41	-4.19	3	1	51.32	Yes (0 violations)	4.7	<chem>CCCCC(C(OC)C(=O)OCC1=C(C=C2=C1C=C2)N</chem>
E022		6.4	6	5.9	448.51	4.12	-6.06	3.58	-4.17	6	0	71.06	Yes (0 violations)	4	<chem>COC1=C(OC2CC2)C=C(C(OC3C(C3)C=C2)=C1)OC1CC1</chem>

	Chemical Structure	pKi (5-HT _{1A})	pKi (5-HT _{2A})	pKi (5-HT _{2B})	MW(Da)	ClogP	ClogS	ClogD	pKa (basic)	HBA	HBD	TPSA (Å ²)	Lipinski Rule	CNS-MPO	SMILES
E023		6.4	5.4	6.1	291.35	1.47	-2.57	1.94	-2.53	4	2	63.71	Yes (0 violations)	5.5	<chem>COCOCOCOC1=CC=CC2=C1C(C=C(CO))=CN2</chem>
E024		6.4	5.5	5.8	174.24	3.68	-4.12	3.44	-4.87	1	0	9.23	Yes (0 violations)	3.9	<chem>C=CC1=CC=CC=C1OC1CC1</chem>
E025		6.5	5.5	5.8	216.32	4.36	-4.91	4.08	-3.36	1	1	20.23	Yes (0 violations)	3.2	<chem>CCC1=CC=C(C=C1)C(O)C1CC1</chem>
E026		6.5	5.7	5.8	400.56	6.4	-6.51	4.77	-6.4	4	0	36.92	Yes 1 violation: MLOGP>4.15	3.4	<chem>CCOC1=CC=CC=C1OCCCCCCCCCOCC1=CC=CC=C1</chem>
E027		6.5	5.2	6	191.23	1.97	-2.82	2.19	-4.05	2	1	34.25	Yes (0 violations)	5.5	<chem>COCOC1=C2C=CC=CC=C2N1</chem>
E028		6.5	5.4	5.7	204.27	3.27	-4.04	3.18	-4.61	2	0	18.46	Yes (0 violations)	4.3	<chem>COC1=CC(OC2CC2)C=CC=C1</chem>
E029		6.5	5.2	5.8	277.32	1.58	-2.46	1.34	-3.83	4	1	60.55	Yes (0 violations)	5.8	<chem>COCOCOCOC(=O)CC1=CC=CC2=C1N=C2</chem>

	Chemical Structure	pKi (5-HT _{1A})	pKi (5-HT _{2A})	pKi (5-HT _{2B})	MW(Da)	ClogP	ClogS	ClogD	pKa (basic)	HBA	HBD	TPSA (Å ²)	Lipinski Rule	CNS-MPO	SMILES
E030		6.5	5.7	5.9	259.31	2.1	-3.04	1.7	-3.24	3	3	65.48	Yes (0 violations)	5.2	<chem>OC1(CC1)C(O)C1=CC=CC2=C1C=CN2)C1(O)CC1</chem>
E031		6.5	6	6	294.39	5.35	-5.76	4.27	-4.56	2	0	18.46	Yes 1 violation: MLOGP>4.15	3	<chem>C=CC1=CC=CC=C1OCCOC2=CC=CC=C2C=C</chem>
E032		6.5	5.3	5.7	312.37	3.66	-5.2	3.49	-4.42	4	0	44.76	Yes (0 violations)	4.9	<chem>COC1=CC(=CC=C1)OCCOC2=CC=CC=C2C=C</chem>
E033		6.5	5.3	5.7	236.31	2.97	-2.58	3.14	-4.02	3	0	27.69	Yes (0 violations)	4.8	<chem>CCOCC1=CC(=CC=C1)OCCOC2=CC=CC=C2C=C</chem>
E034		6.5	5.4	5.7	368.47	1.84	-3.39	2.59	-3.5	6	0	55.38	Yes (0 violations)	5.6	<chem>COCOCOCOC1=CC(=CC=C1)OCCOC2=CC=CC=C2C=C</chem>
E035		6.52	5.2	5.8	402.44	2.46	-3.93	2.95	-3.93	7	0	80.29	Yes (0 violations)	5.2	<chem>CCOC1=CC(=CC=C1)OCCOC2=CC(=CC=C2)C=O</chem>

	Chemical Structure	pKi (5-HT _{1A})	pKi (5-HT _{2A})	pKi (5-HT _{2B})	MW(Da)	ClogP	ClogS	ClogD	pKa (basic)	HBA	HBD	TPSA (Å ²)	Lipinski Rule	CNS-MPO	SMILES
E043		6.6	6	6	460.57	5.88	-6.59	4.82	-4.22	5	0	53.99	Yes (0 violations)	5	<chem>CCOC1=CC(\C=C2)CC(C(=O)C3=C(C)C(OC)C=C3)C2=O)C=C=C1OC1C1</chem>
E044		6.6	6.2	5.7	476.57	4.8	-6.57	4.07	-4.18	5	0	71.06	Yes (0 violations)	3.3	<chem>CCOC1=CC(\C=C2)CC(C(=O)C3=C(C)C(OC)C=C3)C2=O)C=C=C1OC1C1</chem>
E045		6.6	5.8	5.8	310.3	4.25	-5.28	4.01	-4.41	3	0	27.69	Yes (0 violations)	3.8	<chem>CCOC1=CC=C(\C=C2)C(OC)C=C2)C=C1OC1C1</chem>
E046		6.6	5.4	5.8	280.36	2.31	-3.42	2.7	-3.77	4	0	36.92	Yes (0 violations)	5.5	<chem>COCOCOCOC1=CC(COC2CC2)C=C1OC</chem>
E047		6.62	5.4	6	204.27	2.85	-3.5	3.09	-4.61	2	0	18.46	Yes (0 violations)	4.5	<chem>COC1=C(OC2CC2)C=C(C)C=C1</chem>
E048		6.7	5.4	6	381.47	1.17	-2.18	1.88	-3.42	6	1	71.17	Yes (0 violations)	5.7	<chem>COCOCOCOC1=CC(C)C(OC2CC2)C=C1</chem>
E049		6.7	6	5.9	382.5	4.95	-5.45	3.8	-3.78	4	0	36.92	Yes (0 violations)	3.8	<chem>C=CCC1=CC=CC=C1OCCOCCOC1=C</chem>
E050		6.7	5.8	5.9	322.4	4.67	-5.51	4.11	-4.41	3	0	27.69	Yes (0 violations)	3.6	<chem>COC1=C(OC2CC2)C=C(C)C=C1OC3CC3)C=C1</chem>

	Chemical Structure	pKi (5-HT _{1A})	pKi (5-HT _{2A})	pKi (5-HT _{2B})	MW(Da)	ClogP	ClogS	ClogD	pKa (basic)	HBA	HBD	TPSA (Å ²)	Lipinski Rule	CNS-MPO	SMILES
E059		6.78	5.54	5.8	278.39	3.99	-4.21	3.37	-3.79	3	0	27.69	Yes (0 violations)	4.2	<chem>CCCC=CC=C(C2CC2)C=C10CCOCCOC</chem>
E060		6.79	5.64	5.56	362.47	2.9	-4.49	3.16	-3.68	5	0	53.99	Yes (0 violations)	5.4	<chem>CC(=O)C(OC1CCCC1)OC2CCOC2C3=CC=CC=C3</chem>
E061		6.8	5.8	5.67	328.41	2.95	-3.92	3.15	-3.66	4	0	36.92	Yes (0 violations)	5.3	<chem>C1CCCC1=CC=C(C1=CC=CC=C1)OC2CCOC2C3=CC=CC=C3</chem>
E062		6.81	5.5	5.9	218.3	3.22	-3.84	3.42	-4.61	2	0	18.46	Yes (0 violations)	4.2	<chem>CCOC1=C(OC2CC2)C=CC(C=C)C=C1</chem>
E063		6.82	5	5.6	323.39	1.22	-2.51	1.88	-3.52	5	1	61.94	Yes (0 violations)	5.8	<chem>COC1=CC=C(C=C1)OC2CCOC2C3=CC=CC=C3</chem>
E064		6.86	5.57	5.7	364.48	3.98	-4.1	3.48	-3.62	5	0	46.15	Yes (0 violations)	4.7	<chem>CCCC1=C(OC2CCOC2)C=C(C1)OC3CCOC3C4=CC=CC=C4</chem>
E065		6.87	5.55	5.7	259.31	1.18	-2.77	1.1	-3.38	3	4	76.48	Yes (0 violations)	5	<chem>OC(C1=CC=C(C=C1)OC2CCOC2)C3=CC=CC=C3</chem>
E066		6.87	6.1	5.8	396.53	5.13	-5.64	3.85	-3.76	4	0	36.92	Yes (0 violations)	3.7	<chem>C=CC1=CC=C(C=C1)OC2CCOC2C3=CC=CC=C3</chem>
E067		6.9	5.6	5.8	290.4	4.22	-4.5	3.41	-3.79	3	0	27.69	Yes (0 violations)	4.1	<chem>COC1=CC=C(C=C1)OC2CCOC2C3=CC=CC=C3</chem>

	Chemical Structure	pKi (5-HT _{1A})	pKi (5-HT _{2A})	pKi (5-HT _{2B})	MW(Da)	ClogP	ClogS	ClogD	pKa (basic)	HBA	HBD	TPSA (Å ²)	Lipinski Rule	CNS-MPO	SMILES
E076		7.32	5.8	5.9	418.53	2.97	-4.73	3.13	-3.53	6	0	55.38	Yes (0 violations)	5	CCC1=CC=C(OC2(CC2)C2(CC2)OC23CC20CC3)C=C1OCCOCCOC
E077		7.34	5.8	5.9	334.46	3.26	-3.98	3.21	-2.63	4	1	47.92	Yes (0 violations)	5.1	CCC1=CC=C(C=C1)OCCOC(C)C(C1CC1)CC1O
E078		7.36	5.8	5.9	380.44	3.41	-5.27	3.37	-3.78	4	2	68.5	Yes (0 violations)	4.5	C(COCCOCOC1=C2C=CNC2=C(C=C1)OCCOC1=CC=CC2=C1C=CN2
E079		7.36	5.8	5.6	356.46	3.72	-4.2	3.32	-3.66	4	0	36.92	Yes (0 violations)	4.8	C(COCCOCOC1=CC=CC=C1)OCCOC(C1CC1)C1=CC=CC=C1
E080		7.4	5.7	6.1	345.44	2.8	-3.77	3	-3.35	4	2	63.71	Yes (0 violations)	5	COCCOCCOC1=CC=CC2=C1C(=CN2)C(O)C1CC1
E081		7.4	5.3	6	363.45	1.88	-3.46	2.53	-3.52	5	1	61.94	Yes (0 violations)	5.5	COCCOCCOC(COCCOC1=CC2=C(C=C1)NC=C2)CC=C1
E082		7.57	6	5.9	382.5	4.48	-4.79	3.5	-3.66	4	0	36.92	Yes (0 violations)	4.3	C(COCCOC1(CC1)OC1=CC=C(C=C1)OCCOC(C1CC1)C1=CC=CC=C1
E083		7.6	5.7	6	400.51	3.63	-4.46	3.52	-3.64	5	0	46.15	Yes (0 violations)	4.6	CCOC1=CC=CC=C1OCCOC(COCCOC1=CC=C(C=C1)C1=CC=CC=C1
E084		7.7	5.9	6	412.35	4.26	-4.67	3.59	-3.64	5	0	46.15	Yes (0 violations)	4.2	C(COCCOCOC1=CC=CC=C1OCCOC(C1CC1)OCCOC(C1CC1)C1=CC=CC=C1

	Chemical Structure	pKi (5-HT _{1A})	pKi (5-HT _{2A})	pKi (5-HT _{2B})	MW(Da)	ClogP	ClogS	ClogD	pKa (basic)	HBA	HBD	TPSA (Å ²)	Lipinski Rule	CNS-MPO	SMILES
E085		7.85	6.2	5.9	428.59	4.74	-5.48	3.92	-3.78	4	0	36.92	Yes (0 violations)	3.5	<chem>C(COCCSC(C1CC1)C1=CC=CC=C1)OCCOC1=CC=CC=C1C1=CC=CC=C1</chem>
EA		6	6.2	6.26	432.56	2.9	-4.59	2.1	-3.53	6	3	96.22	Yes (0 violations)	4.4	<chem>CC(C)C1=C2C3=CC=C(C1C@H)C@H)C@H)C(C)O[C@H]4[C@@H]([C@H]([C@H]([C@H]([C@H]4O)O)O)O)C=O</chem>
	Erinacine A (Positive Control)														
EAA		5.4	6.3	6.4	300.44	3.85	-4.62	2.87	-3	2	1	37.3	Yes (0 violations)	4.8	<chem>CC(C)C1=C2C3=CC=C(C1C@H)O)C@H)C(C)CC1C@H)C@H)C(C)CC1)C=O</chem>
	Erinacine A Aglycone (Positive Control)														

3. Predicted Advantages

- Synthesis 1–4 steps from commercial precursors
- Superior blood-brain and intracellular barrier penetration (logP 1-5.)
- Elimination of 5-HT_{2B} agonism → no valvulopathy risk
- Activity of MAPK and NF-κB, reduces inflammation and activates neurogenesis
- Sustained NGF/BDNF induction without hallucinogenic effects
- Adjustable elimination half-life via lipophilicity tuning
- Potential telomerase activation and geroprotective properties
- High expected metabolic stability and low toxicity

4. Conclusion

The structures presented in this study demonstrate a broad spectrum of affinity for serotonin receptors, often possess increased potential for penetration across the blood-brain barrier and biomembranes, are free of molecular ballast, and provide a good starting point for precisely determining optimal toxicological and pharmacokinetic properties in subsequent stages of research. The structures are synthesized in 1-4 steps using clean, simple, and accessible pharmacological synthesis methods from readily available starting materials, which is often crucial for lipophilic candidates, terpenes, and terpenoids.

The structures contain fine amphiphilic amine-mimeticity ligands, such as dienes and cyclopropane radicals, polyether chains, and alcohol groups. Thus, not only the allosteric and modulatory properties of the candidates but also their full mimetic properties can be realized. Given their high affinity for serotonin receptors, some of the candidates may exhibit the full spectrum of effects characteristic of potent serotonergic agents, ultralipophilic and amphiphilic, deeply penetrating, potent 5-HT mimetics, hypothetically involved in all of the above-mentioned neuroplastic and geroprotective scenarios.

The *in silico* analysis summarized in the table demonstrates high affinity values for 5-HT and CNS-MPO for the most common pharmacological nuclei, such as indoles and polyether linkages. In contrast, underrepresented diene radicals, cyclopropyl radicals, substituted allylbenzene-based nuclei, and alkylated cinnamic alcohols have low CNS-MPO values. Given that the history of pharmacology is poor in lipophilic, nitrogen-free, centrally active substances (e.g., fentanyl), the *in silico* data are based on heterochemical compounds, and there are no reference standards for non-nitrogenous lipophilic substances other than natural terpenes, terpenoids, and saponins, there is likely significant variability in the assessment of LogP, CNS-MPO, active permeability, and some other parameters. Dynamic calculations of polyethyleneglycol behavior, the high amphiphilicity of cyclopropane and the allyl radical, and the exotic nuclei and radicals of these compounds are extremely challenging for *in silico* evaluation using existing databases and algorithms. Furthermore, the ultra lipophilicity of candidates like hericenones can be interpreted as excessive lipophilicity, but this may be a guarantee of accumulation in the myelin sheath, indicating that existing algorithms are not designed for structures deep regional delivery. Thus, researched structures represent a case of working in a pharmacological blind spot, which introduces some inaccuracies, but also potentially offers great potential for new classes of pharmacological agents and therapeutic approaches.

A wide range of pharmacological properties of structures can also be provided by a large number of fundamentally different new nuclei, which facilitates the development of drugs of various therapeutic classes and is an integral part of the development of drugs for complex pathologies.

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Digital Resources

Affinity calculation SerotoninAI: <https://serotoninai.streamlit.app/>

Definitions of physicochemical characteristics and pharmacokinetic descriptors:

SwissTargetPrediction (<https://www.swissadme.ch/index.php>)

ADMETlab 2.0 (<https://admetmesh.scbdd.com/service/evaluation/cal>)

Chemaxon (<https://chemaxon.com/>)

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